

PROBE WG2 “Advanced ABL profiling” - Deliverable 2.1

Advanced aerosol products

D2.1: Reports, white and review papers on key ABL parameters, their applications, and the end-user requirements.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This report aims at providing a synthesis of aerosol profile products for several applications and end-users with the corresponding existing algorithms. For each group of products several references are provided so that the reader can refer to these for specific products and related applications.

Through all the documents the following acronyms are used:

- ABL: Atmospheric Boundary Layer
- AHL: Aerosol High-power Lidar
- ALC: Automated low-power Lidar Ceilometer
- AOD: Aerosol Optical Depth
- CL: Calibration coefficient of the Lidar
- LR: Lidar Ratio for aerosols
- SNR: Signal to Noise Ratio

2 METHODS OVERVIEW

The most common way of gaining ABL aerosol profiling observations is using the lidar (light detection and ranging) technique. In this document we concentrate on ground-based lidar systems, which can be classified in Aerosol High-power Lidars (AHLs) and Automated low-power Lidar Ceilometers (ALCs), as done within the PROBE and ACTRIS CARS (Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing) / CCRES (Centre for Cloud Remote Sensing) communities. AHL and ALC systems use the same measurement principle (i.e., elastic backscatter from atmospheric aerosols and molecules), but differ in laser power, ability to measure the inelastic (i.e., Raman) scattering at different wavelengths, data accuracy, and degree of automation.

ALCs are low-power, single wavelength backscatter lidars operationally measuring aerosol profiles and cloud base heights. They are spreading within national and international networks (e.g., [E-PROFILE](#)) thanks to their technological advancement and capacity to be easily operated in continuous mode. Some ALCs are also equipped with a polarisation-sensitive channel. AHLs are high-power, research-oriented, multi-wavelength lidars providing aerosol profiles with high accuracy. They are equipped with Raman and/or polarisation-sensitive channels. They are operating within well established national and international networks (e.g., ACTRIS/[EARLINET](#)) but suffer from sparse spatial and temporal sampling.

The retrieval of aerosol properties can be accomplished either at one or at multiple wavelengths, with or without a polarisation-sensitive channel. In general, since the estimation of aerosol properties from lidar systems is an ill-posed problem, a-priori assumptions and/or ancillary measurements (e.g., photometers) are necessary. Photometer measurements are available from various networks, such as [AERONET](#), [SKYNET](#), and [GAW-PFR](#), and can be collocated with lidar systems.

The retrieval of aerosol properties from ALCs has become increasingly important in relation to their capacity to operationally provide information to both the scientific and stakeholder communities. Different methodologies were developed for this purpose, sometimes using significantly different approaches, such as model-derived functional relationships among variables (Dionisi et al, 2018) or specific conversion factors and ancillary data (Mortier et al., 2013). In fact, the aerosol extinction (and, in turn, the extinction-to-backscatter ratio, i.e., the LR) cannot be directly retrieved from ALCs, and the use of ancillary information within the retrieval is needed. On the contrary, the aerosol extinction and backscatter can be directly retrieved from Raman AHLs without any assumption about the LR (Pappalardo et al., 2004), in particular during nighttime (when the background noise is low). During daytime, the retrieval of aerosol optical properties from AHLs rely on the same methodologies applied to elastic backscatter lidars (the forward/backward Klett inversions; Klett, 1988). The lidar signal and the retrieved aerosol optical properties are wavelength-dependent, hence the retrieval procedure and the assumptions (e.g., the LR) must be tailored to the lidar wavelength.

Concerning the retrieval of aerosol physical properties, both ALCs and AHLs must be complemented with ancillary information (e.g., the aerosol density) from collocated sensors / a-priori assumptions / numerical models. In presence of polarisation-sensitive channels, the aerosol retrievals can benefit from the depolarisation information to refine the aerosol microphysical characterisation. It is worth mentioning that both AHLs and ALCs suffer from the incomplete overlap of the laser beam and the receiver field of view in the near range, but this issue is particularly important for AHLs, sometimes hampering ABL profiling.

The main lidar networks currently operating in Europe are:

- [E-PROFILE](#) (Europe): coordinated by MeteoSwiss (financed by EUMETNET)
- [V-Profiles](#) (Norway): coordinated by MetNorway
- [ALICENET](#) (Italy): coordinated by CNR-ISAC
- [Lidarnet](#) (UK): coordinated by MetOffice
- [CEILONET](#) (Germany): coordinated by DWD
- [ICARE-AERIS](#) (France): coordinated by AERIS
- [EARLINET](#) (Europe): coordinated by ACTRIS (this including sub-networks, e. g. SPALINET in Spain and Portugal)

They are mainly coordinated by Weather Services and Research Institutions at national and EU level. Other networks outside Europe are: GALION, Pollynet, ADnet, MPLNet, LALINET.

Lidar networks allow aerosol monitoring at high spatial and temporal resolution. They can provide valuable information to environmental, meteorological, aviation safety agencies (e.g., alerts in case of dust/ash advections), as well as for atmospheric and environmental studies (e.g., aerosol-cloud interactions, atmospheric circulations, radiative balance). Ground-based aerosol profilers are also a valuable resource to evaluate and complement satellite products and model outputs. The former may be limited by the number of overpasses over the same area, the presence of clouds, and complex aerosol stratifications in the lower atmosphere, while the latter by a coarse resolution and a simplified description of atmospheric processes. The assimilation of aerosol profiles into atmospheric and chemistry models (e.g., Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service's [CAMS](#)) is currently under evaluation within different networks. The impacts and main end-users of the aerosol products which

can be derived from lidar systems are more specifically addressed in the PROBE deliverables 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 4.1.

3 PRODUCT OVERVIEW

The main aerosol products which can be retrieved from lidar systems are summarised in this Section. These include:

- Total attenuated backscatter (Sect. 3.1)
- Aerosol backscatter and extinction (+ AOD=integrated extinction over height) (Sect. 3.2)
- Aerosol concentration (mass / volume) (Sect. 3.3)
- Depolarisation (VDR=volume depolarisation ratio / PDR=particle depolarisation ratio) (Sect. 3.4)
- Aerosol typing (Sect. 3.5)
- Aerosol layering and alerts (Sect. 3.6)

For each product, a table listing the main retrieval algorithms developed and currently applied in Europe is reported. For each algorithm, it further summarises the instrumental requirements, the method and status of implementation, the ancillary data and assumptions, the main sources of uncertainty of the results, the data availability, and examples of applications / references / repositories. The reader is referred to the reference list for detailed information on the theoretical and numerical aspects of the algorithms.

The expected accuracy of the aerosol products depends on the magnitude of the respective Main sources of uncertainty. These, in turn, depend on the instrument status, the applied pre-processing procedures (in particular, the calibration and the overlap correction), the accuracy and availability of ancillary information, and the presence of Raman or polarisation-sensitive channels. In general, the accuracy ranges from 10% to 50% for aerosol optical properties, depending on the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the instrument, the availability of Raman measurements, and the applied inversion methodology. For elastic backscatter lidars, the forward Klett inversion was proven to provide aerosol backscatter and extinction profiles with a higher accuracy with respect to the backward inversion (Wiegner et al., 2014; Diémoz et al., 2020). Concerning aerosol physical properties, the accuracy ranges from 20% to over 80%, depending on the available ancillary information, the possibility to adjust the a-priori parameters according to the aerosol conditions under investigation, and the presence of depolarisation profiles.

In general, the product resolution depends on the resolution of the lidar data and on the numerical setup of the retrieval algorithm (see [JND 2a: Automatic low-power Lidar and Ceilometer](#) for ALC instrument settings). For lidar systems, the typical data resolution is of the order of 10 m in space, 10 s in time.

The aerosol retrieval algorithms are mainly identified by the coordinating network. However, it is worth mentioning that they result from joint international efforts, mainly conducted in the framework of EU initiatives (e.g. the Cost Actions [TOPROF](#) and [PROBE](#), the EUMETNET Program [E-PROFILE](#), the H2020 Project [RI-URBANS](#)). Within PROBE, the following Virtual Mobility Grants (VMG) and Short Term Scientific Missions (STSM) were conducted concerning aerosol products:

- [VMG1] Osborne, M. (2022): Implementation of temperature dependent corrections to the overlap functions of CHM15k ALC in the E-PROFILE processing chain
- [VMG2] Bellini, A. (2022): Overview of the current methodologies for the retrieval of aerosol extinction and mass concentration profiles from Automated Lidar-Ceilometers
- [VMG3] Pires Salgueiro, V.C. (2022): Synergy for volcano eruption detection and characterization

- [VMG4] Granados-Muñoz, M.J. (2022): Assessing radiative properties of extreme pollen events observed by synergy remote sensors in South-Eastern Iberian Peninsula
- [VMG5] Buxmann, J. (2023): Investigating the seasonal fluctuations of the CHM15K Ceilometer calibration constant
- [VMG6] Guerrero Rascado, J.L. (2023): Advanced aerosol vertical profiling in drylands: case study of an olive grove
- [VMG7] van Hove, M. (2023): Seasonal variation in the Rayleigh calibration factor of Automatic Lidar-Ceilometers: amplitude across Europe and possible explanations
- [VMG8] Osborne, M. (2023): Project to compare ALC retrieval algorithms on common data sets
- [STSM1] de Morales Céspedes, J.R. (2023): Liquid cloud calibration algorithm for ALC

The reports of the above activities are available at <https://zenodo.org/communities/probe-cost/>.

3.1 TOTAL ATTENUATED BACKSCATTER

Network	Instruments	Method and status of implementation	Ancillary data and assumptions	Main sources of uncertainty	Data availability	Examples of application / papers / repositories
E-PROFILE	ALCs. Tested instruments: Lufft CHM15k, Vaisala CL61 / CL51 / CL31, MiniMPL.	<p>- overlap correction: empirical method for CHM15k (Hervo et al., 2016), manufacturer for Vaisala CL61 / CL51 / CL31.</p> <p>- calibration: Rayleigh method for CHM15k (Wiegner and Geiß., 2012), cloud method for Vaisala CL51 / CL31 (Hopkin et al., 2019). For MiniMPL, a different method is used (see Sect. 3.2) since CLs have shown large variability.</p> <p>Automated and operative in NRT.</p>	<p>Ancillary data: LR, molecular profile, manufacturer overlap function.</p> <p>Assumptions:</p> <p>- overlap correction for CHM15k: homogeneous aerosol layer in the overlap zone during the derivation of the correction, temperature dependent overlap artefacts.</p> <p>- Rayleigh calibration: good SNR in the mid/upper troposphere, aerosol-free calibration window during nighttime, known molecular profile and LR. CL is calculated on a daily basis and the</p>	<p>Main sources of uncertainty:</p> <p>- accuracy and variability of the Rayleigh calibration for CHM15k (VMG1, VMG5, VMG7) and cloud calibration for Vaisala CL51 / CL31 (STSM1). Stability of the manufacturer calibration for CL61.</p> <p>- accuracy of the overlap correction.</p> <p>- SNR, uncorrected instrumental artefacts (e.g., background signal, Kotthaus et al., 2016), water vapour absorption (Wiegner and Gasteiger, 2015).</p>	NRT visualisation at E-PROFILE and V-Profiles .	<p>E-PROFILE Monitoring of aerosol transport events at EU scale</p> <p>Hervo et al., 2016 algorithm to correct for temperature-dependent variations in the overlap function of CHM15k in Switzerland</p> <p>Wiegner and Geiß., 2012 absolute calibration of Jenoptik CHM15kx ceilometer in Munich (Germany)</p> <p>Hopkin et al., 2019 calibration of ceilometers using the integrated backscatter from totally attenuating</p>

			<p>monthly median value is used.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cloud calibration: totally attenuating liquid cloud, no saturation of the detector. - Backward Klett: good SNR in the mid/upper troposphere, aerosol-free calibration window at each inversion. 			liquid clouds, tested in range of climates
ALICENET	<p>ALCs.</p> <p>Tested instruments: Lufft CHM15k, Vaisala CL61.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - overlap correction: empirical method for CHM15k (Hervo et al., 2016), manufacturer for CL61. - calibration: Rayleigh method for CHM15k (Wiegner and Geiß., 2012, Bellini et al., 2024), manufacturer for CL61. <p>Automated and operative in NRT.</p>	<p>Ancillary data: model-derived, pre-calculated aerosol backscatter-to-extinction functional relationship, molecular profile, manufacturer overlap function.</p> <p>Assumptions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - overlap correction for CHM15k: homogeneous aerosol layer in the overlap zone for the derivation of the correction, 	<p>Main sources of uncertainty:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - accuracy and variability of the Rayleigh calibration for CHM15k (VMG1, VMG5, VMG7). Stability of the manufacturer calibration for CL61. - accuracy of the overlap correction. - SNR, uncorrected instrumental artefacts. 	<p>NRT visualisation at ALICENET and data provision under request at alicenet@isac.cnr.it.</p>	<p>Diémoz et al., 2019</p> <p>ALC used to identify pollutant transport at the mesoscale and local air quality impacts</p> <p>Gobbi et al., 2019</p> <p>characterization of dust advections in Rome</p> <p>Tositti et al., 2021</p> <p>characterization of dust transport from East Europe</p>

			<p>temperature dependent overlap artefacts.</p> <p>- Rayleigh calibration: good SNR in the mid/upper troposphere, aerosol-free calibration window during nighttime, known molecular profile, mean continental aerosol type. CL is calculated on a daily basis and the Loess interpolated values are used.</p>			<p>Bellini et al., 2024</p> <p>Monitoring of large-scale transport of desert dust / fires plumes, Etna and Stromboli volcanic plumes, mesoscale pollution advections in Italy.</p>
<p>Lidarnet</p>	<p>ALCs, AHLs.</p> <p>Tested instruments: Raymetrics LR111-300, Lufft CHM15k, Vaisala CL61 and CL31.</p>	<p>- overlap correction: manufacturer, remarks made mainly apply to MetOffice internal retrieval.</p> <p>- calibration: Rayleigh method for CHM15k, manufacturer for CL61, Freudenthaler et al. (2009) for Raymetrics.</p> <p>Automated on internal R&D server</p>	<p>Ancillary data: LR, molecular profile, manufacturer overlap function.</p> <p>Assumptions:</p> <p>- Rayleigh calibration: good SNR in the mid/upper troposphere, aerosol-free calibration window during nighttime, known molecular profile and LR.</p>	<p>Main sources of uncertainty:</p> <p>- accuracy and variability of the Rayleigh calibration for CHM15k (VMG1, VMG5, VMG7). Accuracy and stability of the manufacturer calibration for CL61.</p> <p>- accuracy of the manufacturer overlap correction.</p>	<p>NRT visualisation at E-PROFILE for CHM15k and CL31 / CL61. Data provision at Lidarnet.</p>	<p>Osborne et al., 2019</p> <p>backscatter from saharan dust and biomass burning aerosols</p> <p>Osborne et al., 2022</p>

		for Raymetrics and CL61. Plan to automate for CHM15k.		- SNR, uncorrected instrumental artefacts.		
CEILONET	ALCs. Tested instruments: Lufft CHM15k.	- overlap correction: manufacturer. - calibration: Rayleigh method (Wiegner and Geiß., 2012). Automated.	Ancillary data: LR, molecular profile, manufacturer overlap function. Assumptions: - accuracy of the manufacturer overlap correction. - Rayleigh calibration: good SNR in the mid/upper troposphere, aerosol-free calibration window during nighttime, known molecular profile (from GFS) and LR.	Main sources of uncertainty: - accuracy and variability of the Rayleigh calibration for CHM15k (VMG1, VMG5, VMG7). - accuracy of the manufacturer overlap correction. - SNR, uncorrected instrumental artefacts.	Data provision under request at DWD .	Flentje et al., 2010 Detection of volcanic ash plume at Zugspitze / Hohenpeissenberg (Germany) Flentje et al., 2021 use of vertical profiles of particle backscatter to compare to ECMWF
ICARE-AERIS	ALCs. Tested instruments: MiniMPL.	Backward Klett (see Sect. 3.2) at present. Plan to implement a Rayleigh calibration procedure.	see Sect. 3.2	see Sect. 3.2	Data visualisation at Oraure	Ceamanos et al., 2023 transport of biomass burning plumes across the atlantic

3.2 AEROSOL BACKSCATTER AND EXTINCTION (+ AOD)

Network	Instrument	Method and status of implementation	Ancillary data and assumptions	Main sources of uncertainty	Data availability	Examples of application / papers / repositories
V-Profiles , E-PROFILE (implementation in V-Profiles)	ALCs. Tested instruments: Lufft CHM15k, MiniMPL.	Forward Klett inversion for CHM15k (Wiegner et al., 2014), backward Klett inversion for MiniMPL (Wiegner et al., 2014). Automated and operative in NRT.	Ancillary data: LR (user-defined) / photometer data (nearest AERONET station), molecular profile. Assumption: vertically-constant LR, aerosol type (user-defined LR) / nearly collocated AERONET station.	Main sources of uncertainty: instrument SNR, accuracy of the overlap correction and calibration (from E-PROFILE), LR / photometer data, LR vertical variability.	NRT visualisation and data provision at V-Profiles .	A-Profiles repository. Mortier et al., 2013 volcanic ash plumes over Lille (France) Mortier et al., 2016
ALICENET	ALCs. Tested instruments: Lufft CHM15k.	Forward Klett plus iterative procedure with pre-calculated, model-derived backscatter-to-extinction functional relationship. Automated and potentially operative in NRT.	Ancillary data: backscatter-to-extinction functional relationship, molecular profile. Assumptions: mean continental aerosol type (at present, the functional relationship is optimised for a continental aerosol type, results are therefore more	Main sources of uncertainty: instrument SNR, accuracy of the overlap correction and calibration, aerosol type.	Under request at alicenet@isac.cnr.it .	Dionisi et al, 2018 quantitative retrieval of vertically resolved aerosol backscatter, extinction, volume, and surface area Rizza et al., 2023 comparison with WRF-Chem aerosol profiles Bellini et al., 2024

			accurate in those conditions).			retrieval of aerosol optical and physical properties within ALICENET, and comparison with independent data
Lidarnet	ALCs, AHLs. Tested instruments: Raymetrics LR111-300, Lufft CHM15k, Vaisala CL61.	Forward Klett for CHM15k and CL61 using fixed LR / collocated photometer data. For Raymetrics: during nighttime extinction and backscatter are directly retrieved from Raman measurements (Ansmann et al., 1992). During daytime, as for ALCs. Automated.	Ancillary data: photometer data / a-priori LR, molecular profile. Assumptions: vertically-constant LR in case of elastic only retrieval (i.e., no Raman measurements), aerosol type without depolarisation profiles.	Main sources of uncertainty: instrument SNR, accuracy of the overlap correction and calibration, LR vertical variability in case of elastic only retrieval (i.e., no Raman measurements).	Visualised and made available for Met Office meteorologists.	Vaughan et al, 2018 Canadian forest fire smoke transport Osborne et al., 2019 Raman lidar / sun-photometer products for extinction / AOD / Mass / Depolarisation / lidar ratio
CEILONET	ALCs. Tested instruments: Lufft CHM15k.	Forward Klett with iterative procedure and fixed LR (manually adjusted for specific events). Automated.	Ancillary data: LR, molecular profile. Assumptions: vertically-constant LR, aerosol type.	Main sources of uncertainty: instrument SNR, accuracy of the overlap correction and calibration, LR vertical variability.	Under request at DWD .	Trickl et al, 2015 ozone in boreal fire plumes Flentje et al, 2010 detection of volcanic ash plume Flentje et al., 2021

						use of vertical profiles of particle backscatter to compare to CAMS
ICARE-AERIS	ALCs. Tested instruments: MiniMPL.	Backward Klett inversion (Wiegner et al., 2014) constrained with photometer data. Extinction in the blind zone derived from nephelometer and aethalometer data. Automated.	Ancillary data: photometer, nephelometer and aethalometer data. Assumptions: presence of a clear reference range at each inversion, vertically-constant LR.	Main sources of uncertainty: instrument SNR and presence of aerosols at the reference range, accuracy of the overlap correction, LR vertical variability.	Data visualisation at Oraure	Mortier et al., 2013 volcanic ash plumes over Lille (France) Popovici et al, 2018 ground-based mobile sun photometer measurements of AOD to compare with MODIS AOD
EARLINET	AHLs.	Raman measurements used to directly retrieve aerosol backscatter and extinction during nighttime (D'Amico et al., 2016, Mattis et al., 2016). During daytime, Klett inversion and LR assumption. If depolarisation profiles are available, the aerosol type is directly estimated.	Ancillary data: LR in case of elastic only retrieval (i.e., no Raman measurements). Assumptions: vertically-constant LR in case of elastic only retrieval (i.e., no Raman measurements), aerosol type without depolarisation profiles.	Main sources of uncertainty: accuracy of the overlap correction, LR in case of elastic only retrieval.	Data visualisation and provision at EARLINET .	Mattis et al., 2016 Bovchaliuket al., 2016 aerosol optical properties (extinction coefficient profiles and lidar ratios

		Automated and operative.				
Other algorithms: GRASP DIVA	AHLs, ALCs, photometers and spectrometers	Synergetic approaches. Automated.	Depending on the instrumental setup.	Depending on the instrumental setup.	Depending on the platform.	Giles et al., 2019 AOD with automatic cloud screening and instrument anomaly quality controls Titos et al., 2019 Vertically resolved aerosol optical properties (backscattering, scattering and extinction) in the southern pyrenees

3.3 AEROSOL CONCENTRATION (MASS / VOLUME)

Network	Instrument	Method and status of implementation	Ancillary data and assumptions	Main sources of uncertainty	Data availability	Examples of application / papers / repositories
V-Profiles , E-PROFILE (implementation in V-Profiles)	ALCs. Tested instruments: Lufft CHM15k, MiniMPL.	Pre-calculated extinction-to-mass coefficients (Mie code + aerosol microphysical parameters) for different aerosol scenarios (user-defined). Automated and operative in NRT.	Ancillary data: aerosol scenario (i.e., aerosol microphysical properties). Assumptions: vertically-constant aerosol properties.	Main sources of uncertainty: accuracy of the aerosol extinction profiles, vertical variability of the aerosol properties.	NRT visualisation and data provision at V-Profiles .	A-Profiles repository. Mortier et al., 2013 volcanic ash plumes over Lille (France)
ALICENET	ALCs. Tested instruments: Lufft CHM15k.	Pre-calculated, model-derived backscatter-to-volume functional relationship, plus assumed aerosol density. Automated and potentially operative in NRT.	Ancillary data: backscatter-to-volume functional relationship, molecular profile. Assumptions: mean continental aerosol type (at present, the functional relationship is optimised for a continental aerosol type, results are therefore more	Main sources of uncertainty: accuracy of the aerosol backscatter profiles (note that aerosol backscatter is characterised by an higher accuracy w.r.t. aerosol extinction), aerosol type and density.	Under request at alicenet@isac.cnr.it .	Dionisi et al., 2018 quantitative retrieval of vertically resolved aerosol backscatter, extinction, volume, and surface area Bellini et al., 2024 retrieval of aerosol optical and physical properties within ALICENET, and comparison with independent data

			accurate in those conditions).			
Lidarnet	ALCs, AHLs. Tested instruments: Raymetrics LR111-300, Lufft CHM15k, Vaisala CL61.	Specific extinction coefficients calculated using photometer inversions and T-matrix calculations. For CL61 and Raymetrics, separation of spherical and irregular aerosols (Ansmann et al., 2011). Automated.	Ancillary data: photometer inversions, particle density (e.g., 2.5 g/cm ³ for dust, 1.5 g/cm ³ for sulphate). For CL61 and Raymetrics, depolarisation ratios (e.g., dust = 26%, sulphate = 1%). Assumptions: vertically-constant aerosol properties without depolarisation profiles, otherwise that all coarse mode aerosols are non-spherical.	Main sources of uncertainty: accuracy of the aerosol extinction profiles (e.g., Raman / elastic only route), vertical variability of the aerosol properties without depolarisation profiles, particle densities and depolarisation ratios.	Visualised and made available for meteorologists.	Ansmann et al., 2011 vertical profiles fine-mode particle mass concentrations Osborne et al., 2019 Raman lidar / sun-photometer products for extinction / AOD / Mass / Depolarisation / lidar ratio
CEILONET	ALCs. Tested instruments: Lufft CHM15k.	Literature extinction-to-mass coefficients, values adjustable for specific case studies. Automated.	Ancillary data: extinction-to-mass coefficients. Assumptions: vertically-constant aerosol properties.	Main sources of uncertainty: accuracy of the aerosol extinction profiles, vertical variability of the aerosol properties.	Data provision under request at DWD .	Trickl et al., 2015 ozone in boreal fire plumes Flentje et al., 2010 detection of volcanic ash plume Flentje et al., 2021

						use of vertical profiles of particle backscatter to compare to CAMS
ICARE-AERIS	ALCs. Tested instruments: MiniMPL.	Extinction-to-mass coefficients (Mie code + photometer inversions; Mortier et al., 2013)	Ancillary data: photometer inversions (size distribution, refractive index) Assumptions: vertically-constant aerosol properties.	Main sources of uncertainty: accuracy of the aerosol extinction profiles, vertical variability of the aerosol properties.	Data visualisation at Oraure	Mortier et al., 2013 volcanic ash plumes over Lille (France)
EARLINET	AHLs.	Specific extinction coefficients. If depolarisation profiles are available, separation of spherical and irregular aerosols (Ansmann et al., 2011). Automated.	Ancillary data: specific extinction coefficients, particle densities and depolarisation ratios. Assumptions: vertically-constant aerosol properties without depolarisation profiles.	Main sources of uncertainty: accuracy of the aerosol extinction profiles (e.g., Raman / elastic only), vertical variability of the aerosol properties without depolarisation profiles, particle densities and depolarisation ratios.	Data visualisation and provision at EARLINET .	Ansmann et al., 2011
Other algorithms: GRASP DIVA	AHLs, ALCs, photometers and spectrometers	Synergetic approaches. Automated.	Depending on the instrumental setup.	Depending on the instrumental setup.	Depending on the platform.	Li et al., 2022 Konsta et al., 2021

3.4 DEPOLARISATION (VDR / PDR)

Network	Instrument	Method and status of implementation	Ancillary data and assumptions	Main sources of uncertainty	Data availability	Examples of application / papers / repositories
ALICENET	ALCs with polarisation-sensitive channel. Tested instruments: Vaisala CL61.	Volume linear depolarisation ratios from Vaisala CL61. Automated and operational.	Ancillary data: none.	Main sources of uncertainty: instrument SNR, calibration of the polarisation-sensitive channel (e.g., JND 2a: Automatic low-power Lidar and Ceilometer).	NRT visualisation at ALICENET .	Bellini et al., 2024 Monitoring of large-scale transport of desert dust / fires plumes, Etna and Stromboli volcanic plumes, mesoscale pollution advections in Italy.
Lidarnet	ALCs, AHLs with polarisation-sensitive channel. Tested instruments: Raymetrics LR111-300, Vaisala CL61.	Volume linear depolarisation ratios from Vaisala CL61, particle linear depolarisation ratios retrieved from Raymetrics (Freudenthaler et al., 2009). Automated and operational.	Ancillary data: none.	Main sources of uncertainty: instrument SNR, calibration of the polarisation-sensitive channel (e.g., JND 2a: Automatic low-power Lidar and Ceilometer).	Visualised and made available for meteorologists.	Osborne et al., 2019 Raman lidar / sun-photometer products for extinction / AOD / Mass / Depolarisation / lidar ratio Liu et al., 2024 VDR with BR-lidarnet in China

EARLINET	AHLs with polarisation-sensitive channel.	Particle linear depolarisation ratios retrieved from Raymetrics (Freudenthaler et al., 2009). Automated and operational.	Ancillary data: none.	Main sources of uncertainty: instrument SNR, calibration of the polarisation-sensitive channel.	Data visualisation and provision at EARLINET .	Bravo-Aranda et al, 2015 mineral dust entrainment over Southern Iberian Peninsula
Other algorithms: GRASP DIVA	AHLs, ALCs, photometers and spectrometers.	Synergetic approaches. Automated.	Depending on the instrumental setup.	Depending on the instrumental setup.	Depending on the platform.	

3.5 AEROSOL TYPING

Network	Instrument	Method and status of implementation	Ancillary data and assumptions	Main sources of uncertainty	Data availability	Examples of application / papers / repositories
EARLINET (NATALI)	AHLs.	Aerosol type estimated from Raman and, if present, polarisation-sensitive channel measurements using ANN. Automated.	Ancillary data: none.	Main sources of uncertainty: availability of depolarisation profiles.	Data provision at EARLINET .	Nicolae et al., 2018 ANN to estimate most probable aerosol type from EARLINET profiles

RMI (Royal Meteorological institute of Belgium)	ALCs with polarisation-sensitive channel. Tested instrument: Vaisala CL61.	Aerosol type determined from backscatter and depolarization profiles. Automated.	Ancillary data: threshold parameters.	Main sources of uncertainty: instrument SNR, calibration of the polarisation-sensitive channel (e.g., JND 2a: Automatic low-power Lidar and Ceilometer).	Data provision at RMI.	
Other algorithms: GRASP DIVA	AHLs, ALCs, photometers and spectrometers.	Synergetic approaches. Automated.	Depending on the instrumental setup.	Depending on the instrumental setup.	Depending on the platform.	Titos et al, 2019 Vertically resolved aerosol optical properties (backscattering, scattering and extinction) in the southern pyrenees

3.6 AEROSOL LAYERING AND ALERTS

Network / Algorithm	Instrument	Method and status of implementation	Ancillary data and assumptions	Main sources of uncertainty	Data availability	Examples of application / papers / repositories
STRATfinder	ALCs. Tested instruments: Vaisala CL51 / CL61, Lufft CHM15k.	Mixed layer and ABL heights using variance and gradient analysis of ALC signals, plus Pathfinder approach	Ancillary data: none.	Main sources of uncertainty: instrument SNR, overlap correction, complex aerosol stratifications due to	NRT visualisation at ABL Testbed project	Kotthaus et al, 2020 Stratfinder algorithm for the detection of the Atmospheric

		(de Brunie et al., 2017). Automated and operative in NRT (ABL Testbed project).		the superposition of local and non-local atmospheric dynamics.		Boundary Layer Height with ALCs Barragàn et al., 2023 ABLH and MLH over Madrid https://sirta.ipsl.fr/s/oftware/
ALICENET (ALADIN)	ALCs. Tested instruments: Lufft CHM15k, Vaisala CL61.	Mixed and continuous aerosol layer heights, detection of elevated aerosol layers from total attenuated backscatter profiles (dynamic time warping and continuous wavelet transform techniques). Automated and potentially operative in NRT.	Ancillary data: none.	Main sources of uncertainty: instrument SNR, overlap correction, complex aerosol stratifications.	Under request at alicenet@isac.cnr.it	Bellini et al., 2024 aerosol layer detection and results over the short and long term. Balestrini et al., 2024 correlation between the aerosol layer heights and nitrogen atmospheric depositions in a high-altitude Alpine environment
ROLINET (Romanian lidar network)	ALCs. Tested instruments: Lufft CHM15k.	Detection of lofted atmospheric aerosol layers and estimate of the aerosol load. Automated and operative in NRT.	Ancillary data: photometer data, backward trajectories.	Main sources of uncertainty: instrument SNR, vertical variability of aerosol properties.	Alerts sented to the Romanian Lidar Network.	Adam et al., 2022 automatic detection system of tropospheric heavy aerosol load

<p>Other algorithms:</p> <p>PathfinderTURB</p> <p>STRAT</p>	<p>ALCs.</p>	<p>Detection of ABL height, aerosol layer boundaries.</p> <p>Automated.</p>	<p>Ancillary data: none.</p>	<p>Main sources of uncertainty: instrument SNR, overlap correction, complex aerosol stratifications.</p>	<p>Not applicable.</p>	<p>Poltera et al, 2017</p> <p>retrieve convective boundary layer (CBL) and the continuous aerosol layer (CAL)</p> <p>Morille et al, 2007</p> <p>vertical distribution of cloud and aerosol layers in the boundary layer</p> <p>Pal et al, 2013</p> <p>ABL depth in Paris</p> <p>Haeffelin et al, 2012</p> <p>daytime and nighttime mixing layers in France</p>
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